
Research

Use of frequency-domain 8x2 MIMO equalization to generate and detect high-speed signals at 128 Gbaud (1.8 Tb/s) and 64 Gbaud (1.03 Tb/s)

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Abstract: The aim of this thesis to demonstrate net signal rates of 1 TB/s and 1.8 TB/s, respectively, for 16-bit and 14-bit (4-D) symbol information at 64 and 128 GBaud by precisely equalizing imperfections on both the transmitter and receiver sides using frequency-domain 8x2 multi-input multiple-output nonlinear pre-distortion and linear equalization. These rates were achieved by precisely equalizing imperfections on both sides. The capacity of a digital-coherent transceiver needs to be increased so that it can accommodate an increasing amount of network traffic in a manner that is both efficient and cost-effective. We have focused a lot of their attention on developing transceivers that are capable of operating at rates that are greater than one terabit per second for each wavelength. A fast Fourier transform-based, low-complexity 8x2 MIMO adaptive equalization is capable of providing accurate correction for linear impairments in transceivers. By employing a Volterra filter on the transmitter side (TxNLC), it is possible to improve the signal's quality while simultaneously correcting for the modulator nonlinear driver's response. We show through experimental validation that a SiGe DAC that works quickly and the proposed equalization are capable of producing 16-bit and 14-bit signals at 64 and 128 GBaud.

Keywords: 8x2 MIMO equalization, SiGe DAC, Fourier transform, TxNLC, Silicon-Germanium, PDMIQM.

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Introduction

A digital coherence transceiver's transmission capacity needs to be increased so that it can accommodate an increasing amount of network traffic in a manner that is both efficient and cost-effective. As shown in Figure 1, researchers have focused a lot of their attention on developing transceivers that are capable of operating at rates that are greater than one terabit per second for each wavelength. [1–13] In addition to this, the researchers have focused on the effectiveness of components for optical signal processing and digital signal processors.

Fig. 1: Comparison of the information rate to the net data rate in the studies that were greater than 1 Tbit/s per wavelength.

Processing has made it possible to realize a capacity of more than one terabit per second by utilizing a configurable combination of symbol and data rates consistent with the requirements of a wide variety of applications. This has made it possible to realize a capacity of more than one terabit per second. In this earlier research, the signal was generated using either Complimentary metal-oxide semiconductor operating at high speeds (CMOS) DACs [1-3], silicon-germanium (SiGe) DACs [4-8], transmission of signals using numerous external electrical sources DACs (MUX DACs) [9-13], components for wideband optical interfaces [12-13]. In order to enhance the signal quality for information transfer rates that are greater than 1 terabit per second per wavelength, it is necessary to accurately account consideration of the transceivers' linear and nonlinear limitations. To be more specific, it is imperative that the peak-to-average ratio (PAPR), which is inflated by pre-distortion on the transmitter side, be preserved. In order to accomplish this, it is required to meticulously correct for both the linear and nonlinear impairments that are caused by the transceivers. Decreases in the electrical signal-to-noise ratio are the result of increases in the peak-to-average power ratio (PAPR), which are generated employing DSP methods on the transmitting end, like spectral shaping and digital pre-distortion (SNR). It's possible that a SiGe DAC with a wide analog bandwidth may give a highquality one-sample-per-symbol signal that also has a low peak-to-average power ratio (PAPR) [6]. This is something that's worth looking into. Example: [Introduction] If the signal has a one-sample-persymbol format and there is no digital signal processor (DSP) on the transmitter end, then the transceiver defect can only be corrected by a DSP on the reception end. This is because there is no DSP on the transmitter end. It has been demonstrated that the time-domain complex-valued 8x2 MIMO adaptive equalizer that was suggested in [11] is capable of simultaneously compensating in light of the transceiver's and the transmitter's linear deficiencies at the digital signal processor of the receiver (DSP). However, because the perfect compensation for the flaws provided by the 8x2 equalizer requires a high number of taps, the processing complexity of the time-domain convolutions quickly grows. In this work, we propose a fast Fourier transformbased, low-complexity 8x2 MIMO adaptive equalization with the purpose of providing accurate correction for linear impairments in transceivers. This equalization was put in place in order to compensate for the linear impairments that are present in the transceiver (FFT). By employing a Volterra filter on the transmitter side (TxNLC), it is possible to improve the signal's quality while simultaneously correcting for the modulator-nonlinear driver's response [14]. The TxNLC is designed to solely correct for the nonlinearities that cannot be equalized by the linear 8x2 MIMO equalization. This is done in order to prevent the PAPR from increasing. We show through experimental

validation that the combination of the SiGe DAC's high throughput and the suggested equalization scheme are capable of producing 1-Tb/s and 1.8-Tb/s net rate signals at 16-bit and 14-bit (4-D) symbol information rates, respectively, at 64 and 128 GBaud. These information rates correspond to 16-bit and 14-bit (4-D) symbol information rates.

AN ADAPTIVE 8x2 MIMO IN THE FREQUENCY DOMAIN

Using the time-domain, complex-valued 8x2 MIMO adaptive equalizer in the digital signal processor (DSP) on the receiving end [11], it is possible to make adjustments for linear flaws in both the transmitter and the receiver at the same time. This adjustment can be done simultaneously. The fact that the 8x2 equalizer uses time-domain convolutions, however, raises the bar in terms of the level of complexity required for calculation. This takes place as a consequence of the high number of taps that are necessary for accurate compensation. Because the fast Fourier transform (FFT) converts time-domain convolutions into frequency-domain multiplications, frequency-domain processing, also known as FD processing [15], has the potential to significantly reduce the amount of computational complexity that is required. You can see in Figure 2 how the block design of the 8x2 MIMO adaptive equalization that we utilize is laid out (a). In addition, the computational complexity may be evaluated with the help of Fig. 2(b), which depicts the number of real multiplications as a function of the number of taps. It has been determined that the two parameters are linked together in a linear fashion. Keep in mind that the number of taps in the FD 8x2 MIMO example is equal to a N/2-point FFT if we assume that there will be a 50% reduction in the amount of overlap. When compared to the timedomain (TD) 8x2 MIMO variation, this frequencydomain (FD) MIMO variation has the potential to significantly reduce the number of complex multiplications required. As a result, errors in both TX and RX can be addressed with a higher degree of precision

Fig. 2: (a) The FD 8x2 MIMO adaptive equalizer block diagram, and (b) a graph showing how much computational power is needed in relation to the total number of taps.

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

As shown in Figure 3(a), an experiment was conducted to compare the throughput of 128 GBaud and 64 GBaud signals. A display showing the device's bandwidth (BW) expressed in decibels (dB) is additionally included on each one. Radio frequency (RF) signals were created for transmission using a 128 GSa/s arbitrary waveform generator (AWG) based on a Silicon-Germanium digital-to-analog converter (SiGe-DAC) (Tx). Single-ended linear driver amplifiers with a gain of 11 dB were used to amplify the radio frequency signals used by the lithium-niobate based polarization division

multiplexed in-phase and quadrature modulator (PDMIQM). The carrier signal at 194 THz was used to modulate the pulse density modulation quadrature amplitude modulation (PDM-QAM) signal. An erbiumdoped fiber amplifier was utilized in order to achieve an amplification of the carrier signal from an ITLA that resulted in 25.5 dBm (EDFA). Optical equalization, also known as OEQ, was applied to optical signals that were modulated at 64 and 128 GBaud (Fig. 3 (b) and (c)). To begin, an EDFA on the Rx side amplified the incoming signal before filtering it using an optical bandpass filter. Following that step, the signal was sent to the Tx side (OBPF). Using a coherent receiver that contained an optical hybrid as well as four balanced photo detectors, the signals were picked up. In order to digitize the signal, an oscilloscope with digital storage that was capable of 256 GSa/s was utilized. The offline Tx-DSP and Rx-DSP contributions to the dialogue are illustrated in Figure 3. (a). In order to produce transmitted symbols that were 5 105 bits in length, the Tx-DSP utilized a Mersenne Twister to function as a pseudo-random number generator. For transmission purposes, symbols of this length were utilized. It was necessary to replicate each symbol in order to increase the symbol sequence's sampling rate to 64 GBaud. TxNLC, which is also known as Tx nonlinearity compensation, was attempted, and it was discovered that the most helpful tool was a third-order Volterra filter with memory values of $m_1 = 21$, $m_2 = 15$, and $m_3 = 9$ [14]. This filter had these specific memory value configurations. After the carrier phase had been brought back online, the broadcast symbols as well as the received symbols were analyzed in order to calculate the filter coefficients (CPR). We trained the TxNLC coefficients with a symbol sequence that was distinct from the one that was used to measure the signal quality so that we could prevent overfitting the data. In order to avoid an increase in PAPR, the TxNLC makes up for only the nonlinearity that is not taken into account by the 8x2 MIMO equalization. In order to achieve this goal, the sampling rate of the signal was modified by the Rx-DSP such that it would output two samples for each symbol. We were able to accomplish this objective thanks to a shift in the currency exchange rate. Next, a pilot-assisted digital phase-locked loop with an OH of 1.59% and a 50% overlap cut FD 8x2 MIMO adaptive equalizer were employed to simultaneously adjust for the linear responses in the Tx and Rx, frequency offset compensation, and coarse channel phase recovery. The combined OH of these two sections was the pilot's usual 1.59%. (AEQ).The AEQ's cutting had an overlap of fifty percent in several places. We determined the FD-AEQ-coefficient update using an FD-normalized least-squares technique [15]. This method was quite straightforward. After that, a blind phase search (also known as a BPS) was performed [16] in order to compensate for the phase noise that was still present. Last but not least, we performed an investigation of the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), after first normalizing the generalized mutual information (NGMI) [17].

Fig. 3: (a) Experimental setup and optical spectra of (b) 64- and (c) 128-Gbaud signals with and without OEQ.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the first place, we investigated the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of the 128-Gbaud 256QAM signal. Figure 4(a) illustrates how the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) shifts depending on the block size of the FFT employed in the FD 8x2 amplification equalizer when the AWG output is 480 mVpp. It was discovered that the SNR might be improved by more than 2 dB by using the recommended FD 8x2 AEQ in conjunction with a sufficiently big FFT-block size (2048 or higher). The difference in the optical signal-to-noise ratio (OSNR) that can be seen between the AWG output with and without the TxNLC is shown in Figure 4(b). Because it only adjusted for the nonlinear distortion that was not able to be equalized by the linear equalizer, OSNRs were only slightly lower with the TxNLC than they were without it (also known as the FD 8x2 AEQ). This is due to the fact that the nonlinear distortion will not be able to be corrected by the linear equalization. Figure 4(c) depicts the relationship between the SNR and the OSNR for the FD-AEQ FFT using a block size of 4,096. Because the TxNLC avoided the effects of saturation induced by the driver amplifiers, the peak SNR was able to be enhanced significantly. Next, we compared the information rate of 128- and 64-Gbaud signals when the peak signal-to-noise ratio was present by utilizing PCS signals that were created by a probabilistic amplitude shaping technique [18]. Figure 4 illustrates the information rate vs. NGMI relationship for 128- Gbaud PCS-484QAM and 64-Gbaud PCS-1024QAM signals, respectively. (c). We are able to establish a spectrum of information rates by modifying the entropy of the distribution for the constellation points so that it is consistent with the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution [18]. The computed NGMI was higher than the NGMI maximum when all of the data rates were taken into account [16]. The performance of the transceiver was tuned in the manner described above so that it would be capable of transmitting signals at the maximum information rate of 1.80 TB/s for 128 Gbaud PCS-484QAM and 1.03 TB/s for 64 Gbaud PCS-1024QAM (17.77 20(1-0.826)/1.01590.128 and 19.98 20(1-0.826)/1.01590.64, respectively. We used EDFA to transmit a single-carrier PCS-484QAM signal over a distance of 30 kilometers in a pure silicon-core fiber at a rate of 1.8 terabits per second and 128 gigabauds. This brings us to our final point (e).

Fig. 4: The following are the findings of certain experiments: (a) SNR vs FFT size of an 8x2 MIMO equalizer; (b) OSNR versus peak-to-peak voltage of an AWG output; (c) SNR versus OSNR with or without TxNLC; and (d) information rate versus (e) optical launching power of a 1.8-Tb/s 128-GBaud signal.

CONCLUSIONS

We are able to properly equalize the Tx and Rx flaws thanks to the utilization of frequency-domain 8x2 linear adaptive equalization and nonlinear correction made possible by a Volterra filter. This allows for the defects to be canceled out. Experiments have demonstrated that we are capable of reaching net rates of 1.80 Tb/s at 128 Gbaud PCS484QAM and 1.03 Tb/s at 64 Gbaud PCS1024QAM while carrying out this research. These incredible results could not have been achieved without a net throughput of 1.03 terabits per second on a computer with 64 gigabauds of bandwidth. Extremely high data rates of 16 bits/4D symbols at 64 Gbaud and 14 bits/4D symbols at 128 Gbaud were achieved with the assistance of a high-speed transceiver that is capable of transmitting data at a rate of more than one terabit per second for each wavelength..

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8x2 MIMO adaptive equalization is a promising field of research.

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